

Online supplementary

MATERIAL

Donors and ethical compliance

Our study complies with applicable French regulations and with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Fresh blood samples were collected from asthmatic subjects (men and women aged from 18 to 79) in the Department of Respiratory Diseases at Toulouse University Hospital Center and processed anonymously for peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) purification by Pancoll (PAN-Biotech) gradient separation and then assessed for ILC2 frequency by FACS as described below. Inclusion criteria were asthma defined according to GINA guidelines (<https://ginasthma.org/>) and positive bronchodilator response defined by an increase in FEV₁ and/or FVC \geq of 12% and \geq 200 mL after inhalation of 400 μ g Salbutamol. Controlled and uncontrolled asthma was defined according to GINA guidelines. The study was designed to include similar numbers of subjects for two major age classes (18-39 and 40-79), in order to make sure that females in the younger group were mainly composed of women of childbearing age. This study (RC/31/20/0007) was authorized under agreement number ID-RCB 2020-A00223-36 by the competent ethics board, Comité de Protection des Personnes Nord-Ouest IV (Lilles, France).

Nasal polyp digestion and ILC2 enrichment

Nasal polyps were cut into small fragments and digested with Type I collagenase (6 mg per g of tissu; Sigma-Aldrich) and DNase I (100 μ g per g of tissu; Roche, Basel, Switzerland) for 90 minutes at 37°C. Cells were then filtered through 70 μ m cell strainer and then mixed with human red blood cells (100 blood cells per nucleated cell) for further ILC2 enrichment using the STEMCELL Technologies RosetteSep™ Human ILC2 Enrichment Kit (Catalog number 17197691). Alternatively, ILC2 were directly sorted from NP cells or ILC2-enriched whole blood by flow cytometry as CD45⁺Lin^{neg} CD7⁺ CD161⁺ cells as shown in Fig. S1.

Culture of ILC2s

Enriched ILC2s were expanded for 7 to 10 days in IMDM medium (supplemented with 2% of AB human serum, 0.25% BSA, 1.8 mg/L 2-amino-ethanol, 40 mg/L Apo-transferrin, 5 mg/L insulin and 100mg/L penicillin/streptomycin) on OP9-DL1 with 5 ng/ml each of IL-2, IL-7, IL-25 and IL-33. ILC2 were further expanded in the absence of feeder with the same cytokine cocktails in the presence of 5- α DHT (10⁻⁸M, Sigma-Aldrich) or ostarine (10⁻⁷M, Sigma-Aldrich) for one week.

Single-cell RT-PCR analysis of *AR*- and *GATA-3* gene expression in human ILC2

Human ILC2 prepared from nasal polyp were single cell sorted with a FACS Aria-Fusion cell sorter (BD Biosciences) in a 96-well plate preloaded with a medium containing 2% Triton X-100, 1 U/ μ l RNaseOut recombinant ribonuclease inhibitor (Thermo Fisher Scientific), 940 μ M dNTPs, and 12.5 ng/ μ l random hexamer primers (Thermo Fisher Scientific). After cell sorting, single cell lysates were subjected to RNA reverse transcription using 6.25 U/well Maxima H Minus reverse transcriptase (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Both target genes were PCR-amplified using *AR* or *GATA-3* cDNA-specific primer pairs (Table S1), and negative wells screened out by real-time quantitative PCR (RT-qPCR) with nested primers (Table S1) and SsoAdvanced Universal SYBR Green Supermix (Bio-Rad Laboratories). The qPCR fluorescence-based assays were performed using the automated pipetting system epMotion® 5070 (Eppendorf), and a Light Cycler 480 instrument (Roche). A limit of detection

(LOD) was defined as a Ct value of 23, then, all Ct values higher than the LOD were removed from the analysis. mRNA expression levels were defined as $2^{(LOD-Ct)}$ as described ¹.

AR protein expression by western blot

Cell lysates were prepared in Laemmli sample buffer (Invitrogen), sheared through a 31G needle, and total protein was quantified by a bicinchoninic acid protein assay (Pierce). Reducing agent was next added and samples were heated for 10 minutes at 70°C. Protein (20 µg per lane) were fractionated by SDS-PAGE on precast 4%–15% gradient stain free gels (Bio-Rad). Gels were activated by UV exposure and transferred to Amersham Hybond 0.45-µm PVDF membranes (GE Healthcare). Membranes were blocked with 5% skim milk and 0.1% Tween-20 in PBS, probed overnight with the rabbit anti-AR antibody (Cell Signaling Technology, clone D6F11, #5153) or anti-β-actin (A1978) from Sigma. Primary antibodies were detected with appropriate HRP-conjugated secondary Abs (Cell signaling). Densitometric analysis was performed using Image Lab software v5.0 (Bio-Rad).

Flow cytometry

Human immune cells were stained with the following fluorescent mouse monoclonal antibody (mAb) conjugates against specific surface markers to study human ILC2 : PE-Cy7 anti-human CD45 (BD Biosciences, catalog number 557748); FITC anti-human Lin (Biolegend, catalog number 348701) ; AF700 anti-human CD7 (Biolegend, clone : CD7-6B7) ; PB anti-human CD127 (Biolegend, clone : A019D5), PE anti-human CRTH2 (Biolegend, clone : BM16), APC anti-human CD161 (BD Biosciences, clone : DX12). Cells were analyzed using a LSR-Fortessa (BD Biosciences), and the data were processed with the FlowJo software (FlowJo LLC).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses and data presentation were performed using GraphPad Prism 10 software (La Jolla). All statistical tests were two-tailed and p-values <0.05 were considered to be statistically significant.

Reference

1. Abbas F, Cenac C, Youness A, Azar P, Delobel P, Guery JC. HIV-1 infection enhances innate function and TLR7 expression in female plasmacytoid dendritic cells. *Life Sci Alliance* 2022; 5: e202201452.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1: Clinical characteristics of asthmatic patients

	Total (n=49)	#uncontrolled (n=29)	£controlled (n=20)
Age	*41.1 (+/- 15.9)	38.2 (+/- 14.4)	41.3 (+/- 17.6)
Females	**32 (65.3)	17 (58.6)	15 (75.0)
GINA step			
GINA 1	8 (16.3)	3 (10.3)	5 (25.0)
GINA 2	1 (2.0)	1 (3.4)	0 (0.0)
GINA 3	4 (8.1)	3 (10.3)	1 (5.0)
GINA 4	11 (22.4)	8 (27.6)	3 (15.0)
GINA 5	25 (51.0)	14 (48.3)	11 (55.0)
FEV1	2.9 L (+/- 1.0)	3.2 L (+/- 1.0)	2.4 L (+/- 0.8)

* mean \pm SD

patients with uncontrolled asthma

£ patients with controlled asthma

** number of females (percentage)

Supplementary Table S2

Primer pairs	Sequences 5'-3'	Amplimer size
<i>AR/NR3C4</i> , PCR1	AGAGTGCCCTATCCCAGTCC GGCGCACAGGTA CTTCTGTT	260 bp
<i>AR/NR3C4</i> , real-time PCR2	AGAGTGCCCTATCCCAGTCC CCGGAGTAGCTATCCATCCA	63 bp
<i>GATA-3</i> , PCR1	CCTCAGCCACTCCTACATGG GTGGTGGATGGACGTCTTG	297 bp
<i>GATA-3</i> , real-time PCR2	CACGGTGCAGAGGTACCC AGGGTAGGGATCCATGAAGCA	92 bp

Table S2: AR- and GATA-3-specific primer pairs used for PCR1 and PCR2 in Fig. 1C. We chose primers separated by intronic sequences for the pre-amplification PCR to only amplify mRNAs but not genomic DNA.

Supplemental Figure S1. Gating strategy used to identify blood ILC2 in asthmatic subjects.

Supplemental Figure S2. Human ILC2 expansion from nasal polyps. (A) Experimental protocol: once the human nasal polyp has been recovered and digested, cells of interest were enriched by the Rosette SEP[®] protocol. The ILC2-enriched cells were then cultured in a specific Yssel medium with the survival and ILC2-activating cytokines (IL-7, -2, -25 and -33). (B) Phenotype of ILC2s in culture at day 8. (C) Intracellular IL-13 cytokine production profile of ILC2s after PMA/ionomycin stimulation versus unstimulated cells.